

Public

GRACE README (STUDY OVERVIEW)

Prepared by: Dr Andelija Milic (a.milic@qut.edu.au) and Professor Janet M. Davies (j36.davies@qut.edu.au), Allergy Research Group, Centre for Immunology and Infection Control, Queensland University of Technology, Brisbane, Queensland 4059, Australia

Version: 1.0

Created: 1/07/2026

RECORD TITLE

Global Responses of Airborne Grass Pollen to Climate Change (GRACE): Study Overview

RECORD AUTHORS

Andelija Milic (Queensland University of Technology, QLD, Australia; 0000-0002-5385-999X)

Janet M. Davies (Queensland University of Technology, QLD, Australia; 0000-0002-6378-4119)

RECORD CONTRIBUTORS

Paul J. Beggs (Macquarie University, NSW, Australia; 0000-0001-9949-1783)

Benoit Crouzy (MeteoSwiss, Switzerland; 0000-0002-9911-415X)

Jonathan Peter (University of Cape Town Lung Institute, South Africa; 0000-0002-2658-0723)

German Dario Ramon (Instituto de Alergia e Inmunologia del sur, Argentina; 0000-0001-9990-8147)

Simon Haberle (Australian National University, ACT, Australia; 0000-0001-5802-6535)

Athanasios Damialis (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece; 0000-0003-2917-5667)

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RECORD PURPOSE

This record serves as the registration and transparent, citable documentation package for the **GRACE** study. It contains the summary of the study, proposal for the manuscript, and inclusion framework for choosing the study sites.

The proposed publication is being prepared as part of a series of manuscripts on Aerosol Trends to underpin the Seventh Assessment Report (**AR7**) of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (**IPCC**).

RECORD CONTENTS

- GRACE_study_overview_README.pdf (This file)
- GRACE_study_summary_v1.0.pdf (Short summary of the study background, aims and impact)
- GRACE_manuscript_proposal_v1.0.pdf (Manuscript proposal with study background, research aims, study design and study outputs)
- GRACE_site_inclusion_framework_v1.0.pdf (Criteria used to identify suitable study sites)

RELATED RECORDS

This record contains the GRACE study registration package only. Additional Zenodo records containing metadata and derived datasets will be published as they become available and will be linked to this record.

CITATION

Milic, A. & Davies, J. (2026). Global Responses of Airborne Grass Pollen to Climate Change (GRACE): Study Overview (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20822245>

LICENCE

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